

Assessing Multicollinearity in Population Data Using the Farrar-Glauber Approach

¹ SULAIMON M. O.

² ADEWUNMI O. A.

³ MABOSANYINJE A.

^{1,2,3} *Department of Statistics & Mathematics, Moshood Abiola Polytechnic, Abeokuta, Nigeria.*

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to determine whether multicollinearity exists, how severe it is, where it occurs, and what pattern it exhibits. Additionally, it aims to rectify any multicollinearity between the rates of death, fertility, life expectancy, and maternal mortality. The study covers distribution and trend of multicollinearity in the population rate of Nigeria between 2005 and 2024. The intercorrelation between the different explanatory variables as determined by multiple correlation coefficients was ascertained using tests (chi-square, F-test, and T-test). According to the findings, the degree of multicollinearity was high, as indicated by the Pearson value of 0.9 and the R^2 value of 0.999 (99%). A high presence of multicollinearity in the maternal mortality rate and life expectancy is indicated by the p-value, which also shows that the explanatory factors were statistically significant and that the VIF1, VIF2, and VIF3 are high. Based on the results, we found that the model fits well and that the maternal mortality rate and VIF life expectancy have higher multicollinearity than other factors.

Keywords: Data, Multicollinearity, Population

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria has the largest population in Africa and the sixth largest in the world, with almost 200 million people living in an area of 923,768 km² (356,669 sq mi). It is also one of the most densely populated countries in Africa. Very high birth rates have caused Nigeria's population to grow fast over the past 50 years or more, quadrupling over that time. Following a sharp decline in child mortality in the 1980s, growth peaked, and it has subsequently slowed somewhat as birth rates have decreased.

It is impossible to overstate the importance of population factors on a nation's development. This is due to the fact that most governments' policies and programs, which are all focused on sustainable development, are either directly or indirectly related to population dynamics and features. Development plans, programs, policies, and projects all demonstrate the Nigerian government's dedication to raising the standard of living for its citizens. This is a result of their recognition of the complexity of the relationship between population and development as well as the role that demographic considerations play in the nation's growth. Issues pertaining to the population are currently more widely recognized, as is the necessity of including demographic factors into development planning. The connections between population factors and more general developmental

Received: 20 June 2025

Revised: 25 June 2025

Accepted: 28 June 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

1155

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15836449](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15836449)

issues, such as housing, education, health, agriculture, energy, the environment, gender issues, food security, and the safety of people and property, must be understood by all parties involved.

Nigeria has developed a number of policies, including political, social, demographic, and economic initiatives, in an effort to achieve sustainable development. However, a number of obstacles, including inadequate implementation strategies, corruption, a lack of political will, and others, have made it difficult to realize the development goals set forth by these programs. The National Policy on Population and Sustainable Development is one such policy that aims to develop Nigeria by utilizing its demographic and population characteristics. Therefore, by evaluating the multilinearity in the country's population data, this article aims to evaluate the successes and shortcomings of the national policy on population and sustainable development and how this has affected Nigeria's development.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

In order to address the issue of collinearity or interaction among a few chosen population rates, this study on the test of multicollinearity among some population rates was started. Among other population rates, it mainly covers the death rate and a few causal indicators, such as the life expectancy, fertility, and maternal mortality rates. The government is concerned about death rate statistics, and people are confused about the causes and reasons behind premature deaths. The high death rate in Nigeria can be caused by a failure to take into account and respond to social determinants of health. Furthermore, the health care sector nearly entirely ignores socioeconomic determinants of health, such as growing urbanization and low economic conditions, as major barriers to better coordinated action.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study is to examine whether multicollinearity exists in Nigerian population data. The specific objectives are:

1. Check the country's population rate for the presence of severe multicollinearity.
2. Look for areas where the country's population rate exhibits multicollinearity.
3. Check for the multicollinearity pattern in the country's population rate.
4. To address the multicollinearity in the population rate of the country.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The goal of this study is to use the Farrar-Glauber approach to examine the pattern and location of multicollinearity in population rates. The Nigeria Demography and Health Survey (NDHS) for the years 2005–2024 is the main focus of the study. In order to conduct an efficient research study, the study's scope is focused on Nigeria's population rates.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. Do the listed and illustrated indicators exhibit multicollinearity, and if so, to what extent?
2. Which indicator has a strong multicollinearity presence and existence?
3. Do the indications shown exhibit a location of multicollinearity?
4. Which indicator exhibits an unusual multicollinearity pattern?
5. Of the indicators, which one is in charge of multicollinearity?

STATEMENT OF THE HYPOTHESES

The following hypotheses was stated and tested in this study:

$H_0 : \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = 0$ (There is no existence and severity of multicollinearity among the causative indicators).

$H_1 : \beta_1 \neq \beta_2 \neq \beta_3 \neq 0$ (There is existence and severity of multicollinearity among the causative indicators).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Multicollinearity

According to Cressie (1996), the explanatory variables must not be entirely linearly connected ($r_{xi}r_{xj} \neq 1$) in order for least squares to be applied. The existence of a linear or nearly linear relationship between explanatory variables is referred to as multicollinearity. The method of least squares breaks down and the parameters become indeterminate if the explanatory variables are perfectly linearly adjusted, meaning that the correlation coefficient for these variables is equal to unity. This is because it is difficult to derive numerical values for each parameter separately. At the other extreme, the variables are referred to as orthogonal (variables whose covariance is zero: $\left(\frac{\sum X_i X_j}{n} = 0\right)$ if the explanatory variables are not inter-correlated at all (that is, if the correlation coefficient for these variables is not equal to zero). In this case, there are no issues with the coefficient estimates, at least not in terms of multicollinearity. Actually, a multiple regression analysis is not required when dealing with orthogonal x's. A straightforward regression of y on the matching regressor, $y = f(x)$, can be used to estimate each parameter. Neither of the two extreme scenarios—perfect collinear X's or orthogonal x's—are frequently encountered in practice. Because numerous economic magnitudes are interdependent throughout time, there is typically some degree of inter-correlation among the explanatory variables. Although the precise effects of collinearity have not yet been theoretically established, the multicollinearity issues may affect the precision and stability of the parameter estimates in this scenario, where the simple correlation coefficient for each pair of explanatory variables will have a value between zero and unit.

Due to the nature of economic magnitudes, multicollinearity is a phenomenon that is inherent in most relationships rather than a condition that either occurs or does not exist in economic function. There is no solid proof of the level of collinearity, which if it exists, will have a significant impact on the parameter estimation. Naturally, it becomes quite challenging to determine the impact of each regressor on y independently when any two explanatory variables are changing in a manner that is almost identical. Assume, for instance, that a person's consumption expenditures are influenced by his income and liquid assets. The impact of one of these variables on consumption may be mistakenly attributed to the other if income and liquid assets vary by the same amount over time. Because of their significant inter-correlation, it is not reasonable to examine how these variables affect consumption (Aldrich, 2005).

Multicollinearity's nature

Ragnar is credited with coining the term multicollinearity (2013). Originally, it denoted that some or all of the explanatory variables in a regression model had a "perfect," or exact, linear connection. According to strict definitions, colinearity is the existence of a single linear relationship involving explanatory variables x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k (where $x_1 = 1$ for all observations to allow for the intercept term) and multicollinearity is the existence of multiple exact linear relationships. An exact linear relationship is considered to exist if the following condition is met: $\lambda_1 x_1 + \lambda_2 x_2 + \dots + \lambda_k x_k = 0$, where $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_k$ are constants that aren't all zero at the same time.

The assumption's plausibility

Since it is extremely uncommon for any two variables to precisely inter-correlate in a linear form, the multicollinearity unit's assumption that the variables are not fully linearly correlated is, in theory, easily met in practice. However, a less than perfect intercorrelation between the explanatory variables may have a significant impact on the least squares estimates (Fotheringham, 2002).

Motives behind multicollinearity

Received: 20 June 2025

Revised: 25 June 2025

Accepted: 28 June 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

1157

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15836449](https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15836449)

First, economic variables have a propensity to move in tandem over time. The same factors affect economic magnitudes, and as a result, once these deciding factors take effect, the economic variables exhibit the same general pattern or behavior across time. For instance, the fundamental economic magnitudes increase during booms with high economic expansion, while some tend to lag behind others. As a result, during economic expansion, income, consumption, savings, investment, prices, and employment tend to increase, whereas during recession, they tend to fall. In certain series, the most significant cause of multicollinearity is growth and trend factors. Second, some explanatory variables' lagged values are used as independent, independent factors in the connection. In several areas of practical econometrics, models with distributed lags have shown good results, and their use is rapidly growing. For instance, in the function of consumption. It is now common practice to incorporate both historical and current income levels as explanatory factors. Distributed lags pertaining to historical economic activity levels are also added as distinct explanatory variables in the investment function. Naturally, there is a correlation between the consecutive values of some variables. For instance, income in the present period is somewhat based on its value in the preceding period, and so on. Therefore, in distributed lag models, multicollinearity is essentially a given.

It is evident from the aforementioned factors that most economic interactions should exhibit some degree of collinearity. While multicollinearity is typically associated with time series, it is also extremely common in cross-sectional data. For instance, labor and capital inputs are nearly always highly associated in the sample of manufacturing firms across all sections because small firms typically have lesser quantities of both labor and capital, whereas large firms typically have larger quantities of both. However, in time series, multicollinearity is typically more prevalent and a more significant issue.

Multicollinearity's impacts

1. The coefficient's estimates are uncertain.
2. The matrix $(X'X)$ becomes singular, meaning that the standard errors of these estimations become infinite.
3. Even if there is a clear statistical relationship between the dependent variable and the collection of independent factors, the regression coefficients are still statistically significant.

Repercussions of multicollinearity

When multicollinearity is present, the estimate of the influence of one variable on y after adjusting for the others is typically less accurate than if the predictors were uncorrelated. A regression coefficient is typically interpreted as an estimate of the impact of changing an independent variable, X_1 , by one unit while keeping the other variables unchanged. We only have observations for which X_1 and X_2 have a specific relationship (either positive or negative) if X_1 and another independent variable, X_2 , in the given data set have a high correlation. Our estimates of the impact of independent changes in X_1 are imprecise because we lack examples for which X_1 changes independently of X_2 . In a way, the collinear variables provide the same information about the dependent variable, according to Kutner (2004).

Measures that are ostensibly "different" but actually quantify the same thing are redundant. Alternatively, if the variables are allocated separate names and perhaps employ different numeric measurement scales yet are significantly connected with one other then they suffer from redundancy. The tendency for the standard errors of the impacted coefficients to be high is one of the characteristics of multicollinearity. In that scenario, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected when the hypothesis that the coefficient is equal to zero is tested against the alternative that it is not equal to zero. Nevertheless, the coefficient will be shown to be significant if a straightforward linear regression of the dependent variable on this explanatory variable is estimated; in other words, the analysis will reject the hypothesis that the coefficient is unimportant. An analyst may mistakenly

believe that there is no linear relationship between an independent and dependent variable when multicollinearity is present. Overfitting in regression analysis models is the main risk associated with such data redundancy. Regression models with predictor analysis models that have a high correlation with the dependent (outcome) variables but have a weak correlation with one another are the best. This type of mode is frequently referred to as "low noise" and is statistically resilient, meaning it will make accurate predictions over multiple samples of variable sets taken from the same statistical population.

METHODOLOGY

The location and pattern of multicollinearity in Nigerian population rates were investigated using the Farrar Glauber test. Multicollinearity in a sample is defined by Farrar and Glauber as a deviation of the observed X's from orthogonality. The general notion that the regression coefficients become indeterminate if multicollinearity is perfect gave rise to their methodology. Additionally, multiple correlation coefficients and partial correlation coefficients can be used to measure the inter-correlations between the different explanatory variables.

The following is an outline of the test:

1. To determine the degree of multicollinearity in a function with several explanatory factors, the first test is a chi-square test.
2. If the chi-square test is affirmative, the second test, the F-test, is used to determine which variables are multi-collinear.
3. If the F test is affirmative, the third test is a t-Test to identify the pattern of multicollinearity, which is to identify which factors are in charge of the emergence of multi-collinear variables.

The Chi-Square test

The Chi-Square test is performed using the following procedures:

1. One may argue that multicollinearity is an optimal deviation from orthogonality. Farrar-Glauber proposed the following X's test to determine the degree of multicollinearity across the entire set of explanatory variables based on the fact that the stronger the departure from orthogonality, that is, the closer the value of the determined to zero, the stronger the degree of multicollinearity.

Here, the fundamental hypothesis is:

H₀: The X's are orthogonal Vs H₁: The X's are not orthogonal

2. Determine the simple correlated coefficients' matrix (r_{ij}) between x₁. For example, x_i becomes x₁, x₂, and x₃ if there are three explanatory variables.

$$3. \begin{bmatrix} 1 & rx_2x_3 & rx_2x_3 \\ rx_2x_3 & 1 & rx_2x_3 \\ rx_2x_3 & rx_2x_3 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

4. Calculate D = |r_{ij}| the determinant of the matrix (r_{ij})

5. Calculate the Statistics (Farrar and Glauber have found that the quantity) $\chi^2 = - [T - 1 - 1/6(2k + 5)] \text{Log}_e$ (value of the std. determinant)

Where χ^2_{cal} = observed compound from the sample.

T size of the sample, and K = number of explanatory variable has a χ^2 distributed with V = 1/2k (k-1) degrees of freedom.

6. Check χ^2_a with 1/2k (k-1) degrees of freedom (α is the level of significance). It should be clear that the theoretical value of χ^2_{cal} , is the value that defines the critical region of the test at the chosen level of significance and with the appropriate degrees of freedoms.

If the observed χ^2_{cal} is greater than the theoretical value of χ^2 with 1/2k (k-1) degrees of freedom, we reject the assumption of orthogonality, that is, we accept that there is multicollinearity in the function. The higher the observed χ^2_{cal} , the more severe is the multicollinearity. If the observed $\chi^2_{cal} < \chi^2$, we

accept the assumption of orthogonal, that is we accept that there is no significant multicollinearity in the function.

An F-Test for multicollinearity location

Multicollinearity is present if the results of the chi-square test are positive. Finding the multi-collinear factors is the next stage. Using an F-test, Farrar-Glauber calculates the multiple correlation coefficients between the explanatory variables (Rx1,2....x2....x3.....xn, Rx2,2....x1,2...x3.....xn1) and assesses their statistical significance.

Steps:

Write the x_i which is suspected to be inter-correlated with other X_s ' as a function of other X_s ' . Thus, $x_i=f(x_1, x_2, x_3 \dots x_k)$. This can also be rewritten as (Given x_2x_3 as inter-correlated variable then), $X_i=f(x_2x_3)=> B_2 X_2+B_3 X_3+U$

- i. Compute the parameter $b = \begin{pmatrix} b_2 \\ b_3 \end{pmatrix}$ as $b = (x_1 \ x)^{-1} X_i \ X$, where $X = (x_2x_3)$
- ii. Compute $R_i^2 = \frac{b_2 \sum x_1 x_2 + b_3 \sum x_1 x_3}{\sum x_1^2}$ Where $x_i x_j = \frac{\sum x_i x_j - \sum x_i \sum x_j}{T}$

$$\frac{R_i^2}{(k-1)}$$
- iii. Compute the F – statistic $F = \frac{(1-R_i^2)}{(T-K)}$ And check $F_{0.5} (k-1, T-k)$ from the F-distribution table.
- iv. Define the hypothesis H_0 : x_i is not inter-correlated with x_2 and x_3
 H_1 : x_i is inter-correlated with x_2 and x_3
- v. If $F_{0.5} < F_{cal}$, accept H_1 and conclude that x_1 is inter-correlated with x_2 and x_3
- vi. Repeat the test for other x_{ii} suspected to be inter-correlated with others.

A T-test for the multicollinearity pattern

This T-test seeks to identify the factors that contribute to multicollinearity. We calculate the partial correlation coefficients between the explanatory factors and use the t-statistic to analyze their statistical significance in order to identify the variables that are causing the multicollinearity. Keep in mind that, when all other variables are held constant, the partial correlation coefficient between any two variables, x_i and x_j , indicates the degree of correlation between them.

The following formulas provide the partial correlation coefficients for the two-variable model:

$$r^2_{x_1x_2...x_3} = \frac{(r_{12} - r_{12}r_{23})^2}{(1 - r_{23}^2)(1 - r_{13}^2)}$$

$$r^2_{x_1x_2...x_3} = \frac{(r_{13} - r_{13}r_{23})^2}{(1 - r_{23}^2)(1 - r_{12}^2)}$$

$$r^2_{x_1x_2...x_3} = \frac{(r_2 - r_{21}r_{31})^2}{(1 - r_{13}^2)(1 - r_{12}^2)}$$

The basic hypothesis here is

$H_0: r x_i x_j \dots x_1 \dots x_2 \dots x_n = 0$ and is tested against alternative hypothesis $H_1: r x_i x_j \dots x_1 \dots x_2 \dots x_n \neq 0$

Having estimated the partial correlation coefficients, we test their significance by computing for each of them the statistic.

$$t^* = \frac{(r_{x_i x_j \dots x_k}) / \sqrt{T - k}}{\sqrt{1 - r^2_{x_i x_j \dots X_1 \dots X_2 \dots X_k}}}$$

Where $r^2_{x_i x_j \dots x_1 \dots x_2 \dots x_k}$ denotes the partial correlation coefficient between x_i and X_j . The observed value t^* is compared with the theoretical t value with $v = (T - K)$ degrees of freedom at the chosen level of significance). If $t^* > t$, we accept that the partial correlation coefficient between the variable X_i and X_j is significant, that is, the variables X_i and X_j are responsible for multicollinearity in the function. If $t^* < t$ we accept that X_i and X_j are not the cause of multicollinearity, since their partial correlation coefficient is not statistically significant. With the above three statistics, we find the severity, the location and the pattern of multicollinearity.

DATA ANALYSIS

Year	Death Rate	Fertility Rate	Life Expectancy	Maternal Mortality Rate (MMR)
2005	17.842	6.122	46.376	112.684
2006	17.660	6.099	46.775	109.775
2007	17.479	6.075	46.752	106.865
2008	17.298	6.051	46.940	103.956
2009	16.863	6.023	47.504	101.031
2010	16.428	5.995	48.068	98.106
2011	15.993	5.966	48.632	95.180
2012	15.558	5.938	49.196	92.255
2013	15.123	5.910	49.760	89.330
2014	14.800	5.876	50.198	86.458
2015	14.478	5.842	50.636	83.587
2016	14.155	5.808	51.074	80.715
2017	13.833	5.774	51.512	77.844
2018	13.510	5.740	51.950	74.972
2019	13.201	5.675	52.396	72.406
2020	12.892	5.611	52.842	69.840
2021	12.583	5.546	53.288	67.274
2022	12.274	5.482	53.734	64.708
2023	11.965	5.417	54.180	62.142
2024	11.771	5.349	54.494	60.662

Coefficients:

Intercept	Fertility rate	Life expectancy	MMR
51.89660	-0.98005	-0.66902	0.02623

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-0.034372	-0.011234	0.002239	0.013712	0.027811

Coefficients: Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)

Intercept	51.896603	1.846194	28.110	4.77e-15 ***
Fertility rate	-0.980048	0.085099	-11.517	3.72e-09 ***
Life expectancy	-0.669020	0.025926	-25.805	1.82e-14 ***

Received: 20 June 2025

Revised: 25 June 2025

Accepted: 28 June 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15836449>

MMR	0.026232	0.003964	6.618	5.91e-06 ***
Signif. Codes	0 '***'	0.001 '***'	0.01 '*'	0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error	0.01854 on 16 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared	0.9999
Adjusted R-squared	0.9999
F-statistic	7.529e+04 on 3 and 16 DF
p-value	< 2.2e-16

FARRAR GLAUBER APPROACH

1st step: Chi-square

Overall Multicollinearity Diagnostics

MC results detected

Determinant X'X	0.0002	1
Farrar chi-square	147.0278	1
Red Indicator	0.9829	1
Sum of Lambda Inverse	533.2830	1
Theil's Method	0.9472	1
Condition Number	1098.3150	1

1 --> COLLINEARITY is detected by the test

0 --> COLLINEARITY is not detected by the test

> qchisq(.95,df=3)

[1] 7.814728

2nd step: F-test

All Individual multicollinearity diagnostics result

	VIF	TOL	Wi	Fi Leamer	CVIF	Klein	IND1
Fertility rate	22.1689	0.0451	179.9357	381.0404	0.2124	-0.0008	00.0053
Life expectancy	272.6053	0.0037	2308.6451	4888.8955	0.0606	-0.0100	00.0004
MMR	238.5088	0.0042	2018.8250	4275.1588	0.0648	-0.0087	00.0005

IND2

Fertility rate	0.9721
Life expectancy	1.0142
MMR	1.0137

1 --> COLLINEARITY is detected by the test

0 --> COLLINEARITY is not detected by the test

* all coefficients have significant t-ratios

R-square of y on all x	0.9999
------------------------	--------

	Death_rate	fertility_rate	life_expectancy	MMR
Death_rate	1.0000000	0.9710800	-0.9995396	0.9984780
fertility_rate	0.9710800	1.0000000	-0.9769916	0.9736580
life_expectancy	-0.9995396	-0.9769916	1.0000000	-0.9978838
MMR	0.9984780	0.9736580	-0.9978838	1.0000000

Received: 20 June 2025

Revised: 25 June 2025

Accepted: 28 June 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15836449>

3rd step: T test

\$estimate

	Death_rate	fertility_rate	life_expectancy	MMR
Death_rate	0.000000e+00	3.724320e-09	1.823687e-14	5.912989e-06
fertility_rate	3.724320e-09	0.000000e+00	1.262837e-09	8.663220e-05
life_expectancy	1.823687e-14	1.262837e-09	0.000000e+00	1.872143e-04
MMR	5.912989e-06	8.663220e-05	1.872143e-04	0.000000e+00

\$p.value

	Death_rate	fertility_rate	life_expectancy	MMR
Death_rate	0.000000e+00	3.724320e-09	1.823687e-14	5.912989e-06
fertility_rate	3.724320e-09	0.000000e+00	1.262837e-09	8.663220e-05
life_expectancy	1.823687e-14	1.262837e-09	0.000000e+00	1.872143e-04
MMR	5.912989e-06	8.663220e-05	1.872143e-04	0.000000e+00

\$statistic

	Death_rate	fertility_rate	life_expectancy	MMR
Death_rate	0.00000	-11.516553	-25.804736	6.617910
fertility_rate	-11.516553	0.00000	-12.409886	5.205748
life_expectancy	-25.804736	-12.409886	0.00000	4.823326
MMR	6.61791	5.205748	4.823326	0.00000

	Intercept	fertility_rate	life_expectancy	MMR
K=0	51.89660	-0.98005	-0.66902	0.02623
K=1	10.00798	2.01988	-0.19171	0.03130
K=2	10.72727	1.64598	-0.15169	0.02477
K=3	11.33877	1.37938	-0.12586	0.02055
K=4	11.80389	1.18537	-0.10762	0.01757
K=5	12.16255	1.03868	-0.09402	0.01535
K=6	12.44580	0.92409	-0.08348	0.01363
K=7	12.67458	0.83217	-0.07506	0.01226
K=8	12.86299	0.75684	-0.06820	0.01113
K=9	13.02073	0.69398	-0.06248	0.01020
K=10	13.15468	0.64075	-0.05765	0.00941
K=11	13.26981	0.59509	-0.05351	0.00874
K=12	13.36980	0.55550	-0.04993	0.00815
K=13	13.45745	0.52084	-0.04679	0.00764
K=14	13.53490	0.49025	-0.04403	0.00719
K=15	13.60384	0.46305	-0.04158	0.00679

Coefficients: for Ridge parameter K= 0

	Estimate	Estimate (Sc)	StdErr (Sc)	t-value (Sc)	Pr(> t)
Intercept	51.8966	256.0471	28.0687	9.1222	< 2.2e-16 ***
Fertility rate	-0.9800	-1.0055	0.0847	-11.8710	< 2.2e-16 ***
Life expectancy	-0.6690	-7.9006	0.2970	-26.5989	< 2.2e-16 ***

Received: 20 June 2025

Revised: 25 June 2025

Accepted: 28 June 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15836449>

MMR	0.0262	1.8953	0.2778	6.8216	< 2.2e-16 ***
Signif. Codes	0 '***'	0.001 '**'	0.01 '*'	0.05	0.1 ' ' 1

Ridge Summary

R2	adj-R2	DF ridge	F	AIC	BIC
0.99990	0.99990	2.99999	79999.79931	-157.96804	-95.06621

Ridge minimum MSE	0.172591
P-value for F-test (2.99999 , 17.00001)	1.829542e-35

Coefficients: for Ridge parameter K= 1

	Estimate	Estimate (Sc)	StdErr (Sc)	t-value (Sc)	Pr(> t)
Intercept	10.0080	-76.7150	14.2005	-5.4023	< 2.2e-16 ***
fertility_rate	2.0199	2.0724	0.1553	13.3424	< 2.2e-16 ***
life_expectancy	-0.1917	-2.2640	0.1413	-16.0204	< 2.2e-16 ***
MMR	0.0313	2.2616	0.1433	15.7812	< 2.2e-16 ***
Signif. codes	0 '***'	0.001 '**'	0.01 '*'	0.05	0.1 ' ' 1

Ridge Summary

R2	adj-R2	DF ridge	F	AIC	BIC
0.55420	0.50170	0.78110	88.46954	-24.04096	36.65145

Ridge minimum MSE	0.172591 at K= 0
P-value for F-test (0.7811 , 18.99804)	5.897152e-08

Coefficients: for Ridge parameter K= 2

	Estimate	Estimate (Sc)	StdErr (Sc)	t-value (Sc)	Pr(> t)
Intercept	10.7273	-57.9023	16.8960	-3.4270	0.0029 **
fertility_rate	1.6460	1.6888	0.1758	9.6046	<2e-16 ***
life_expectancy	-0.1517	-1.7913	0.1693	-10.5813	<2e-16 ***
MMR	0.0248	1.7894	0.1702	10.5141	<2e-16 ***
Signif. codes:	0 '***'	0.001 '**'	0.01 '*'	0.05	0.1 ' ' 1

Ridge Summary

R2	adj-R2	DF ridge	F	AIC	BIC
0.35350	0.27740	0.61412	37.60062	-7.12509	53.40105

Ridge minimum MSE	0.172591 at K= 0
P-value for F-test (0.61412 , 19.1287)	5.268524e-05

Received: 20 June 2025

Revised: 25 June 2025

Accepted: 28 June 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15836449>

Coefficients: for Ridge parameter K= 3

	Estimate	Estimate (Sc)	StdErr (Sc)	t-value (Sc)	Pr(> t)
Intercept	11.3388	-45.6072	17.2280	-2.6473	0.0161 *
fertility_rate	1.3794	1.4152	0.1768	8.0027	<2e-16 ***
life_expectancy	-0.1259	-1.4863	0.1729	-8.5957	<2e-16 ***
MMR	0.0205	1.4848	0.1735	8.5600	<2e-16 ***
Signif. codes:	0 '***'	0.001 '**'	0.01 '*'	0.05	0.1 ' ' 1

Ridge Summary

R2	adj-R2	DF ridge	F	AIC	BIC
0.244900	0.156100	0.508430	24.700668	1.173375	61.594281

Ridge minimum MSE	0.172591 at K= 0
P-value for F-test (0.50843 , 19.23039)	0.0007455428

Coefficients: for Ridge parameter K= 4

	Estimate	Estimate (Sc)	StdErr (Sc)	t-value (Sc)	Pr(> t)
Intercept	11.8039	-36.8891	16.6958	-2.2095	0.0399 *
fertility_rate	1.1854	1.2162	0.1703	7.1394	<2e-16 ***
life_expectancy	-0.1076	-1.2709	0.1677	-7.5788	<2e-16 ***
MMR	0.0176	1.2696	0.1681	7.5545	<2e-16 ***
Signif. codes:	0 '***'	0.001 '**'	0.01 '*'	0.05	0.1 ' ' 1

Ridge Summary

R2	adj-R2	DF ridge	F	AIC	BIC
0.179600	0.083100	0.434250	19.174713	6.175329	66.522371

Ridge minimum MSE	0.172591 at K= 0
P-value for F-test (0.43425 , 19.31283)	0.002789324

Coefficients: for Ridge parameter K= 5

	Estimate	Estimate (Sc)	StdErr (Sc)	t-value (Sc)	Pr(> t)
Intercept	12.1626	-30.3766	15.8712	-1.9139	0.0711
fertility_rate	1.0387	1.0657	0.1614	6.6031	<2e-16 ***
life_expectancy	-0.0940	-1.1103	0.1595	-6.9625	<2e-16 ***
MMR	0.0154	1.1091	0.1597	6.9437	<2e-16 ***
Signif. codes:	0 '***'	0.001 '**'	0.01 '*'	0.05	0.1 ' ' 1

Ridge Summary

R2	adj-R2	DF ridge	F	AIC	BIC
0.137400	0.035900	0.379120	16.173655	9.539108	69.831256

Ridge minimum MSE	0.172591 at K= 0
P-value for F-test (0.37912 , 19.38041)	0.005968369

Coefficients: for Ridge parameter K= 6

	Estimate	Estimate (Sc)	StdErr (Sc)	t-value (Sc)	Pr(> t)
Intercept	12.4458	-25.3243	14.9775	-1.6908	0.1075

Received: 20 June 2025

Revised: 25 June 2025

Accepted: 28 June 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15836449>

fertility_rate	0.9241	0.9481	0.1520	6.2384	<2e-16 ***
life_expectancy	-0.0835	-0.9858	0.1505	-6.5495	<2e-16 ***
MMR	0.0136	0.9848	0.1507	6.5339	<2e-16 ***
Signif. codes:	0 '***	0.001 '**	0.01 '*	0.05	0.1 ' ' 1

Ridge Summary

R2	adj-R2	DF ridge	F	AIC	BIC
0.10840	0.00350	0.33646	14.30805	11.96283	72.21250

Ridge minimum MSE	0.172591 at K= 0
P-value for F-test (0.33646 , 19.43652)	0.00967153

Coefficients: for Ridge parameter K= 7

	Estimate	Estimate (Sc)	StdErr (Sc)	t-value (Sc)	Pr(> t)
Intercept	12.6746	-21.2898	14.1041	-1.5095	0.1479
fertility_rate	0.8322	0.8538	0.1429	5.9746	<2e-16 ***
life_expectancy	-0.0751	-0.8865	0.1418	-6.2536	<2e-16 ***
MMR	0.0123	0.8855	0.1419	6.2401	<2e-16 ***
Signif. codes:	0 '***	0.001 '**	0.01 '*	0.05	0.1 ' ' 1

Ridge Summary

R2	adj-R2	DF ridge	F	AIC	BIC
0.08780	-0.01960	0.30247	13.04283	13.79496	74.01079

Ridge minimum MSE	0.172591 at K= 0
P-value for F-test (0.30247 , 19.48365)	0.01341578

Coefficients: for Ridge parameter K= 8

	Estimate	Estimate (Sc)	StdErr (Sc)	t-value (Sc)	Pr(> t)
Intercept	12.8630	-17.9934	13.2850	-1.3544	0.1917
fertility_rate	0.7568	0.7765	0.1345	5.7750	<2e-16 ***
life_expectancy	-0.0682	-0.8053	0.1335	-6.0312	<2e-16 ***
MMR	0.0111	0.8045	0.1337	6.0192	<2e-16 ***
Signif. codes:	0 '***	0.001 '**	0.01 '*	0.05	0.1 ' ' 1

Ridge Summary

R2	adj-R2	DF ridge	F	AIC	BIC
0.07250	-0.03660	0.27474	12.13118	15.22975	75.41796

Ridge minimum MSE	0.172591 at K= 0
P-value for F-test (0.27474 , 19.52368)	0.01693133

Coefficients: for Ridge parameter K= 9

	Estimate	Estimate (Sc)	StdErr (Sc)	t-value (Sc)	Pr(> t)
Intercept	13.0207	-15.2492	12.5309	-1.2169	0.2387
fertility_rate	0.6940	0.7120	0.1267	5.6188	<2e-16 ***
life_expectancy	-0.0625	-0.7378	0.1260	-5.8581	<2e-16 ***
MMR	0.0102	0.7371	0.1261	5.8471	<2e-16 ***

Received: 20 June 2025

Revised: 25 June 2025

Accepted: 28 June 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

Signif. codes:	0 ‘***	0.001 ‘**	0.01 ‘*’	0.05	0.1 ‘ ’ 1
----------------	--------	-----------	----------	------	-----------

Ridge Summary

R2	adj-R2	DF ridge	F	AIC	BIC
0.06090	-0.04960	0.25165	11.44443	16.38436	76.54958

Ridge minimum MSE	0.172591 at K= 0
P-value for F-test (0.25165 , 19.55814)	0.02010098

Coefficients: for Ridge parameter K= 10

	Estimate	Estimate (Sc)	StdErr (Sc)	t-value (Sc)	Pr(> t)
Intercept	13.1547	-12.9293	11.8422	-1.0918	0.2887
fertility_rate	0.6408	0.6574	0.1197	5.4933	<2e-16 ***
life_expectancy	-0.0576	-0.6808	0.1190	-5.7195	<2e-16 ***
MMR	0.0094	0.6801	0.1191	5.7093	<2e-16 ***
Signif. codes:	0 ‘***	0.001 ‘**	0.01 ‘*’	0.05	0.1 ‘ ’ 1

Ridge Summary

R2	adj-R2	DF ridge	F	AIC	BIC
0.05180	-0.05970	0.23215	10.90915	17.33393	77.47973

Ridge minimum MSE	0.172591 at K= 0
P-value for F-test(0.23215 , 19.58803)	0.02289015

Coefficients: for Ridge parameter K= 11

	Estimate	Estimate (Sc)	StdErr (Sc)	t-value (Sc)	Pr(> t)
Intercept	13.2698	-10.9421	11.2151	-0.9757	0.3416
fertility_rate	0.5951	0.6106	0.1133	5.3902	<2e-16 ***
life_expectancy	-0.0535	-0.6319	0.1127	-5.6060	<2e-16 ***
MMR	0.0087	0.6313	0.1128	5.5964	<2e-16 ***
Signif. codes:	0 ‘***	0.001 ‘**	0.01 ‘*’	0.05	0.1 ‘ ’ 1

Ridge Summary

R2	adj-R2	DF ridge	F	AIC	BIC
0.04470	-0.06770	0.21547	10.48056	18.12883	78.25802

Ridge minimum MSE	0.172591 at K= 0
P-value for F-test(0.21547 , 19.61417)	0.02530928

Coefficients: for Ridge parameter K= 12

	Estimate	Estimate (Sc)	StdErr (Sc)	t-value (Sc)	Pr(> t)
Intercept	13.3698	-9.2210	10.6442	-0.8663	0.3973
fertility_rate	0.5555	0.5699	0.1075	5.3040	<2e-16 ***
life_expectancy	-0.0499	-0.5896	0.1070	-5.5114	<2e-16 ***
MMR	0.0081	0.5890	0.1070	5.5023	<2e-16 ***
Signif. codes:	0 ‘***	0.001 ‘**	0.01 ‘*’	0.05	0.1 ‘ ’ 1

Ridge Summary

Received: 20 June 2025
Revised: 25 June 2025
Accepted: 28 June 2025
Copyright ♥ authors 2025

R2	adj-R2	DF ridge	F	AIC	BIC
0.03890	-0.07420	0.20101	10.12990	18.80406	78.91885

Ridge minimum MSE	0.172591 at K= 0
P-value for F-test(0.20101 , 19.63726)	0.0273902

Coefficients: for Ridge parameter K= 13

	Estimate	Estimate (Sc)	StdErr (Sc)	t-value (Sc)	Pr(> t)
Intercept	13.4574	-7.7157	10.1239	-0.7621	0.4554
fertility_rate	0.5208	0.5344	0.1022	5.2309	<2e-16 ***
life_expectancy	-0.0468	-0.5526	0.1017	-5.4314	<2e-16 ***
MMR	0.0076	0.5520	0.1018	5.4226	<2e-16 ***
Signif. codes:	0 '***'	0.001 '**'	0.01 '*'	0.05	0.1 ' ' 1

Ridge Summary

R2	adj-R2	DF ridge	F	AIC	BIC
0.034200	-0.079400	0.188380	9.837784	19.384869	79.487090

Ridge minimum MSE	0.172591 at K= 0
P-value for F-test(0.18838 , 19.65775)	0.0291682

Coefficients: for Ridge parameter K= 14

	Estimate	Estimate (Sc)	StdErr (Sc)	t-value (Sc)	Pr(> t)
Intercept	13.5349	-6.3881	9.6487	-0.6621	0.5160
fertility_rate	0.4902	0.5030	0.0973	5.1682	0.0001 ***
life_expectancy	-0.0440	-0.5200	0.0970	-5.3627	<2e-16 ***
MMR	0.0072	0.5194	0.0970	5.3543	<2e-16 ***
Signif. codes:	0 '***'	0.001 '**'	0.01 '*'	0.05	0.1 ' ' 1

Ridge Summary

R2	adj-R2	DF ridge	F	AIC	BIC
0.03030	-0.08380	0.17724	9.59078	19.88979	79.98092

Ridge minimum MSE	0.172591 at K= 0
P-value for F-test(0.17724 , 19.67608)	0.03068141

Coefficients: for Ridge parameter K= 15

	Estimate	Estimate (Sc)	StdErr (Sc)	t-value (Sc)	Pr(> t)
Intercept	13.6038	-5.2085	9.2138	-0.5653	0.5785
fertility_rate	0.4630	0.4751	0.0929	5.1137	0.0001 ***
life_expectancy	-0.0416	-0.4910	0.0926	-5.3032	<2e-16 ***
MMR	0.0068	0.4905	0.0926	5.2951	<2e-16 ***
Signif. codes:	0 '***'	0.001 '**'	0.01 '*'	0.05	0.1 ' ' 1

Ridge Summary

R2	adj-R2	DF ridge	F	AIC	BIC
0.027000	-0.087500	0.167360	9.379221	20.332861	80.414152

Ridge minimum MSE	0.172591 at K= 0
P-value for F-test(0.16736 , 19.69254)	0.03196393

	Fertility rate	Life expectancy	MMR
k=0	22.16891	272.60531	238.50882
k=1	0.08244	0.06824	0.07017
k=2	0.04490	0.04162	0.04207
k=3	0.02984	0.02852	0.02870
k=4	0.02149	0.02083	0.02092
k=5	0.01627	0.01588	0.01594
k=6	0.01276	0.01252	0.01255
k=7	0.01029	0.01012	0.01014
k=8	0.00847	0.00835	0.00837
k=9	0.00710	0.00701	0.00702
k=10	0.00603	0.00597	0.00598
k=11	0.00519	0.00514	0.00515
k=12	0.00452	0.00448	0.00448
k=13	0.00397	0.00393	0.00394
k=14	0.00351	0.00348	0.00349
k=15	0.00313	0.00311	0.00311

Summary of results

Parameter	Linear (Model I)
VIF	Fertility rate (22.1689) Life expectancy (272.6053) MMR(238.5088)
R ²	0.999
ANOVA	F value (7.528e ⁺⁰⁴) p-value (2.2e ⁻¹⁶) (significant)
Fertility rate	Positive (significant)
Life expectancy	Positive (significant)
MMR	Positive (significant)
B ₁	-0.98005
B ₂	-0.66902
B ₃	0.02623

Interpretation of results

The table above shows the Pearson correlations or correlation matrix among the variables. It shows that the Pearson’s correlation coefficients of fertility rate and MMR had positive values which are indication of increasing relationships between them and the rest independent variables show a negative relationship. From the study, the residual standard error value of the estimated regression coefficient was computed. The correlation matrix shows that the degree of multicollinearity was as high as 0.9.

The R square, R adjusted, R and std. error of the estimate shows how good is the model used to fit the data. The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.999 implies that approximately 99.9% of the variation in Death rate is being explained by the auxiliary variable. In other words, Auxiliary variables contribute approximately 99.9% to the death rate. This implies that the model is a good fit.

Multiple regressions were used to estimate the relationship between the dependent and the independent variables. It was also used to determine the effect of death rate on population data in the presence of possible multicollinearity problem. The p value results indicated that all the independent variables in the model were statistically significant. The linear relationship between the variables can be written as:

$$\text{DEATH RATE} = 51.89 - 0.98(\text{FEERTILITY RATE}) - 0.66 (\text{LIFE EXPECTANCY}) + 0.02(\text{MMR})$$

From the regression ANOVA table, which yielded a Sig-value of $2.2e^{-16}$ which is less than the conventional 0.05 level of significance, implies that all the independent variables (fertility rate, life expectancy and MMR) do jointly exert significant impact on Death rate.

The table shows that VIF1, VIF2, and VIF3 are high and LE and MMR are correlated which indicate a strong or high multicollinearity. There are three variance inflations factor. For example, we can interpret ($\sqrt{22.1689} \approx 5$), ($\sqrt{272.6053} \approx 17$) and ($\sqrt{238.5088} \approx 15$) as telling us that the standard error for F.R is 5 times, L.E is 17 times and MMR is 15 times larger than it would have been without collinearity. Fertility rate, life expectancy Maternal Mortality Rate is suspected of causing multicollinearity since their VIF is greater than 5.

Multicollinearity problems were detected in the data, by examining the correlation matrix, VIF and condition index. Since multicollinearity is present in the data,

The first step of Farrar-Glauber value of the standardized determinant is found to be 0.0002 which is very small. The Chi-square result detection is 1 thereby implying the presence of multicollinearity in the model specification. This induces us to go for the next step of Farrar – Glauber test (F – test) for the location of the multicollinearity.

The VIF, TOL and W_i columns provide the diagnostic output for variance inflation factor, tolerance and Farrar-Glauber F-test respectively. The VIF for the variable ‘life expectancy’ is quite high (272.6053) followed by the variable ‘MMR’ (238.5088) and ‘fertility rate’ (22.1689). The degrees of freedom is $(k-1, n-k)$ or (7,8) Thus, the VIF shows that either the variable ‘fertility rate’ or ‘life expectancy’ or ‘maternal mortality rate’ will be the root cause of multicollinearity.

From the analysis Life expectancy and MMR has the highest p values of $1.872143e^{-04}$ and a very low value of t statistics of 4.823326 which indicate that life expectancy and MMR are responsible for the presence of multicollinearity.

As expected, the high partial correlation between ‘Life expectancy’ and ‘MMR’ were found to be highly statistically significant. Similar is the case for ‘MMR and fertility. Not only that even some of the low correlation coefficients are also found to be highly significant. Thus, the Farrar-Glauber test points out that life expectancy and MMR are responsible for the existence of multicollinearity in Nigeria population rates for the variables and period under study.

Remedial measures

Multicollinearity leads to small characteristic roots and when characteristic roots are small, the standard error of β is large which implies an imprecision in the least squares estimation method. Remedial measures such as ridge regression was use to solve the problem of multicollinearity, Ridge regression was applied to estimate the impact of death rate on population data. The ridge regression model described the relationship between the independent variables and dependent variable starting from the analysis we got the suitable parameter k from seq (0, 15) for extracting the estimate values of β coefficient and constructed for a new model with all explanatory variables included.

The shows that the variance inflation factor (VIF) of a ridge regression analysis has been reduced to smaller values. When $K=0$, the VIF shows the presence of multicollinearity because all the

explanatory variables variance are greater than 5, which indicate the presence of multicollinearity and also equivalent to the output result from the 2nd stage of Farrar-Glauber Test.

Since the Ridge regression is aimed mainly to identify value of the ridge parameter k in such a way to reduce the variance term of the slope parameter. From the table we got the suitable parameter k from seq (1, 15) for extracting the estimate values of the variance inflation factor (VIF), in which all values are lesser than 5 and also imply that there is no presence of multicollinearity.

CONCLUSION

It is clear from the research that Farrar-Glauber can easily identify the pattern and location of multicollinearity in Nigeria's population rate, as well as its presence and severity. We found that the presence of multicollinearity in the Nigerian population rate was caused by Life Expectancy and Maternal Mortality Rate (MMR). According to the report, Nigeria has a high prevalence of maternal deaths, which hinders the country's economic development between 2005 and 2024.

REFERENCES

- Cressie, N. (1996) "Change of Support and the Modifiable Area Unit Problem" *Geographical Systems* 3: 169 – 180.
- David A. Freedman (2005), *Statistical Models: Theory and Practice*, Cambridge University Press.
- Fotheringham, AS; Wong, DWS (1st Jan, 2002). "The Modifiable Area Unit Problem in Multivariate Statistical Analysis" in *Environment and Planning. A.* 23(7): 1025 – 1044.
- Kutner, M.H., C.J Nachtshein, and J. Neter (2004), *Applied Linear Regression Models.* 25(7): 25 – 31.
- Smith, J.B. (1997). Effects of eighth-grade transition programs on high school retention and experiences. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 90 (3): 144 – 152
- Thirwal, Dolf (2007) "Growth and Development with Special Reference to Developing Economies", University of Kent at Canterbury, 5 th Edition. 111 (8): 143 – 155
- Tofallis, C. (2009). "Least Squares Percentage Regression". *Journal of Modern Applied Statistical Methods.* 7: 526 – 534.
- Waegeman, Willem; De Baets, Bernanrd; Boullart, Luc (2009). "Roc analysis in Ordinal Regression Learning" *Pattern Recognition Learning*" *Pattern Recognition Letters.* 29:1-9.
- Yang Jing Long (2009). "Human Age Estimation by Metric Learning for Regression Problems". 21(6): 74 – 82.